

IRRIGATION OF LOCAL WATERMELON VARIETIES

¹Davlatova M.A., ²Sarimsakov M.M.

1.Davlatova Maftuna Axmadovna, base doctoral student,

2.Sarimsakov Maksudkhon Musinovich, doctor of Agricultural Sciences.

National Research University "Tashkent Institute of irrigation and agricultural mechanization
engineers" Bukhara Institute of Natural Resource Management

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Abstract. *In this article, the early-mid-season watermelon varieties recommended for cultivation in our country, the local "Sweet" and "Blessing of the East" varieties, are discussed. the results of the scientific research conducted on the study of its effects are presented.*

Keywords: *local variety, watermelon, " Sweet ", "Blessing of the East", soil type, salinity, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, irrigation, standard, egatlab, drip, fruit, yield.*

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Today, at a time when the population of the entire earth is growing rapidly, global climate change, drought and water scarcity are increasing year by year, modernization of the country's agriculture, its export and gross domestic product development of output potential, improvement of agricultural production on the basis of new, modern technologies, increase of efficiency of use of land and water resources, management of farming system based on resource-saving advanced technologies are important and important tasks facing all leaders and experts, as well as scientists and researchers dollar is one of the issues.

As noted in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PDc-4947, "Strengthening of macroeconomic stability and high economic it is necessary to focus on solving issues such as maintaining growth rates, modernization and rapid development of agriculture.

Decision PDs-3978 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 17, 2018 "On additional measures to increase the efficiency of the export of fruit and vegetable products to foreign markets" serves as a program for solving the above tasks

It is known that irrigated agriculture has long been developed in Central Asian countries, mainly in Uzbekistan. Fruit and fruit products grown in Uzbekistan have been popular since time immemorial and have gained fame in many countries of the world with their sweet taste [5,7,10,11,14].

After the independence of our country, the ancient values were restored and gradually developed, and today the cultivation of local polis products occupies an important place not only in agriculture, but also in other economic sectors [5,19,20].

In 2023, more than 3.0 million tons of sugarcane crops were grown in the cultivated areas of our country, and most of them were grown in Afghanistan, the Republic of Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Mongolia, the UAE, Poland, Russia, Ukraine, Estonia, It was exported to countries such as Pakistan, China, and Germany [5,21].

Existing problems. One of the main problems observed in the agriculture of our country up to the present day of the 21st century is water shortage. Year by year increasing water shortage, effective use of water resources in the face of global climate change, increasing the volume of products grown per 1 m³ of irrigation water, supplying the country's domestic markets with

agricultural products, and developing measures to increase the export potential output, improvement of the existing ones is the main task set before our experts and scientists.

According to the 2024 "National Report" of the Cadastre Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of January 1, 2024, 58.21 percent of the land area of our republic is intended for agriculture. is a tool. The area of agricultural land types is 21205.5 thousand hectares, of which 3701.0 thousand hectares are irrigated lands. In addition, 827.3 thousand hectares or 1.84 percent of the total land area are water fund lands.

In these areas, soil fertility, salinity, seepage depth, their mineralization, water supply are different, and irrigation farming requires different approaches [14,18,19,20,24,25].

We are committed to the effective use of land and water resources in agriculture, increasing the weight of the product obtained per hectare of irrigated area and irrigation water, reducing labor and various resource costs, and expanding scientific research aimed at stabilizing the ecological state of the environment. is one of our main goals [4,18,19,20].

Experimental method. In the cultivation of local varieties of watermelon "Shirin" and "Sharq Nemati" in the conditions of alluvial soils of the Bukhara region, traditional soil irrigation and drip irrigation technologies are used. two types, i.e. soil moisture before irrigation were studied in the order of 65-70-65% and 70-75-70% according to Limited field wet capacity [5,6,8,9,19,20,22].

All field and laboratory observations in research were carried out on the basis of methodological manuals of Scientific Research Institute of agrotechnologies of cotton selection, seed production and cultivation (former Uzbekistan cotton Scientific Research Institute), Tashkent Institute of irrigation and agricultural mechanization engineers and Scientific Research Institute of irrigation and water problems, Scientific Research Institute of vegetable, pulses and potato growing.

Soil conditions of Bukhara region consist of groups of alluvial-meadow, brownish-gray and desert sandy, meadow-swamp saline soils (77% of the total cultivated area) [5,13,22].

The climate of the experimental area is sharply continental, with hot summers, hot summers, and cold winters. In June, July hot summer winds cause the rapid evaporation of moisture from the plants and the destruction of crop elements, while the gusty winds in the winter cause the rapid evaporation of moisture from the soil in cultivated land. The Bukhara oasis is divided into regions with a dry climate, semi-desert desert, and semi-desert. There is little precipitation in the region even in autumn and winter months, the main part of atmospheric precipitation falls on spring months.

Research results. The original homeland of watermelon is South Africa, it is a heat-loving and drought-resistant plant. Today, 15 local and 32 foreign varieties of watermelon are recommended for cultivation in the agriculture of our country.

The local "Shirin" variety of watermelon is considered to be an early-mid-ripening variety, the weight of 1 fruit is around 4-5 kg, the sugar content is 11.0-11.45, the yield is around 30-35 s/ha, it is resistant to water and transportation. is distinguished by "Sharq Nemati" is an early-mid-ripening variety, the weight of the fruit reaches 12 kg, the sugar content is 10.9-11.0%, dark red color, medium resistance to transportation, yield 39-41 is s/ha [4,5,9].

These varieties are distinguished by their marketability in the domestic and foreign markets, their taste is sweet, and they are grown in large areas by pressing them over the ground and irrigating them in furrows.

The size of the experimental field is 55x120 m, the number of options is 3, the area of each option is 900 m², the total area of each plot is 8100 m², or the total experimental area is 1.62 ha.

In the experimental field, the seeds of the local varieties of watermelon "Shirin" and "Sharq Ne'mati" were planted on April 18 in 2023, and on May 5 in 2024 due to the abundance of spring rains in the scheme of 180x70x60x1.

In the experimental field, mineral fertilizers of ammonium nitrate (33-34%), ammonium sulfate (21%), urea (46%) and simple superfat (14-18%) were applied before fall plowing and stratification during the growing season. lanned. N-150 kg/ha, P-100 kg/ha and K-50 kg/ha were used in the experimental system.

Irrigation was carried out in two different ways, i.e. 5 times over the traditional land (control option) and 23 times through the drip irrigation system.

The agrophysical and agrochemical properties of the soils of the experimental field were studied by taking samples at the beginning of the experiment and at the end of the growing season.

The soil of the experimental area consists of alluvial soils, which are irrigated from the escutcheon, and the seepage water is located at a depth of 1.8-2.5 meters, low salinity, the humus content in the 0-50 cm layer of the soil .87-1.16%, total nitrogen is 1.23-1.46%, phosphorus is potassium. Before starting the experiment, it was observed that the marginal field moisture capacity of the soil was around 20.6% in the 0-50 cm layer, 21.4% in the 0-70 cm layer, and 22.5% in the 0-100 cm layer. Based on this, irrigation standards were determined in experimental options [24, 25].

Also, the level of soil salinity was analyzed in the experimental field, and it was observed that Cl-0.023%, SO₄-0.060%, Ca-0.02% and Mg-0.007% were around in the 0-30 cm soil layer. It was found that the soils of the experimental field belong to the group of low salinity soils of chloride sulfate type.

In the scientific research carried out in the experimental field, soil preparation for planting, phenological observations such as sowing, seed germination, growth and harvest, analysis of agrophysical, water-physical and agrochemical properties of the soil, calculation of irrigation water things like getting were done.

In the first year of the experiment, the first sprouts began to appear 5 days after the date of planting watermelon seeds, and by April 25, 94-97% of the seedlings sprouted in the nests. It was observed that it is around 13.19-13.30 thousand bush/ha, the number of ripe fruits per bush is on average 3.2-4.7 pieces in the field where "Sweet" variety is planted according to variants, "Blessing of the East" variety was around 3.4-5.1 pcs. The weight of one piece of watermelon was 4.3 kg on average in the "Sweet" variety, and 4.9 kg in the "Blessing of the East" variety (Table 1).

Table 1

Growth and yield of watermelon varieties (2-year average)

Tracking options	Irrigation order, in % relative to ChDNS	Palak length, cm (as of July 1)			The number of formed fruits, pieces, (as of July 1)	Extreme productivity, t/ha
		2023 year	2024 year	average		
"Sweet" variety						
1	65-70-65	119,5	115,3	117,4	3,2	183,0
2	65-70-65	178,3	164,7	171,5	4,3	245,9
3	70-75-70	206,4	194,8	200,6	4,7	268,8

"Blessing of the East" variety						
1	65-70-65	213,4	204,5	209,0	3,4	221,2
2	65-70-65	269,8	254,2	262,0	4,6	297,3
3	70-75-70	298,6	287,1	292,9	5,1	330,1

In the experiment, the influence of irrigation methods on their growth, yield and water economy in the cultivation of local varieties of watermelon "Shirin" and "Sharq Ne'mati" was studied. was compared to the irrigation method (control). In the control option, both watermelon varieties were carried out 5 times in the order that the moisture content of the soil before irrigation was 65-70-65% compared to its marginal field moisture capacity. In this case, the irrigation standards averaged 820-1130 m³/ha in two years, and the seasonal irrigation standards equaled 5065 m³/ha. The number of irrigations is 11-12 times, seasonal irrigation norms are 3025 m³/ha, in the variants of the experiment, in which the drip irrigation method is used, and the soil is irrigated in the order of 65-70-65% relative to the marginal field moisture capacity. 2040 m³/ha of water was saved per hectare compared to the control option. The soil moisture before irrigation of the experiment is 70-75-70% relative to its marginal field moisture capacity. In the drip-irrigated options, the number of irrigations is 13-14 times, seasonal water consumption is 3550 m³/ha according to the varieties. , compared to the control, 1515 m³/ha of water was saved. When studying the effect of irrigation methods and procedures on the productivity of watermelon varieties, the best result was 268.8 t/ha in the variant "Sweet" with drip irrigation in the order of 70-75-70%, and 330 in the "Blessing of the East" variety. was 1 t/ha.

Figure 1. Seasonal watering norms of watermelon varieties (two-year average)

Conclusions. Based on the results obtained from the conducted research, it can be concluded that in the conditions of low salinity grassland alluvial soils of the Bukhara oasis, which have been irrigated since ancient times, high yield of local varieties of watermelon "Sweet" and "Blessing of the East" and irrigation It was observed that it is appropriate to use the drip irrigation method in the order of 70-75-70% relative to the marginal field moisture capacity of the soil in order to use water resources efficiently.

Recommendations. In order to obtain a yield of 269-330 t/ha from the local "Sweet" and "Blessing of the East" varieties of watermelon in the conditions of the alluvial soils of the Bukhara region, which have been irrigated since ancient times, and to save water resources used for

irrigation by 30-39%. it is recommended to irrigate them 12-14 times, at the rate of 280-320 m³/ha, in the order of 70-75-70% relative to the marginal field moisture capacity of the soil.

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